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ON-LINE COURSE ON ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS: STUDENTS' EXPERIENCE WITH PILOT COURSE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

Engineering marvels have enabled to have a better quality of human life and society needs an increasing number of engineers [1]. Common practice of higher education institutions is to incorporate mathematics knowledge and skills into engineering education [2].

This paper presents an alternative approach to fostering mathematics skills in engineering education: undergraduate student skill development in an online course created by an international team of academics. The purpose of this paper is to present the preliminary results of a pilot study of an engineering mathematics online

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course. This study draws on feedback questionnaires of students from Portugal, Spain, Poland, Romania and Estonia.

Preliminary results indicate that the students had very little experience with the subject covered before joining their class. They found the theoretical materials to be helpful and had little to no difficulties in understanding them. The practice tests were of high quality and offered a good feedback and were aligned with the theoretical materials. There was more than enough time to solve assessment tests and most felt that doing the assessment activities would help them both in the final assessment and in real life. Students found the materials easy to use as with nice graphics and not too much text. The platform was easy to navigate and the material presented in a logical, intuitive way. Some students felt the performance of used platform could be improved and it would be beneficial to add assessment tests from multiple subjects, not only for each section.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 International project

Mathematics and its associated subjects are fundamental elements of engineering education and an engineer is expected to demonstrate proficiency in the area. The contemporary skillset of undergraduates includes a degree of sophistication in the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) within their daily lives as well as within the higher education environment.

To meet these standards an ERASMUS+ project was launched. The project unites educators from six countries: the TTK University of Applied Sciences from Estonia (project coordinator), the Letterkenny Institute of Technology from Ireland, the Polytechnic Institute of Porto from Portugal, the University of the Basque Country from Spain, the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca from Romania and the Koszalin University of Technology from Poland. One of the main goals of the project is the development of a 3 ECTS engineering mathematics online course. The purpose of this paper is to present the preliminary results of a pilot study of an engineering mathematics online course.

1.2 Development of the online course in engineering mathematics

The project started with the identification of common mathematics topics and the discussion of modern pedagogical principles. Analysis of the structure and teaching specifications of subjects related to mathematics in partner's institutions has been developed. Due to several differences among all the partners' curricula including number of credits, period of teaching, different syllabus in similar subjects, different number of hours for one ECTS etc, the consortium has formulated a common core for all partners and possible particularities depending on the characteristics of the country or of the degree. The analysis showed that students had the same problems in the partner institutions. Students 'ICT readiness is taken for granted, but it hinders students' learning. Also cultural, linguistic and social barriers need to be considered. A common language of mathematics is expected to be necessary in intercultural

programs, but it is not enough. Course materials should be available in local language - sharing across borders is not easy. It needs to be ensured that local support measures consider local concerns. Automated assessment accounts only with the outcome of assessment, not the process. Smart assessment systems place a significant cognitive burden on assessors, assessment designers and students. The detailed overview with comparative needs analysis has been published 2019 [4]. The consortium has defined the aim of the online course as following: the aim is to develop basic knowledge and practical skills in the mathematical sub-area of Matrices, Determinants and Systems of Linear Equations related to Engineering. Direct target groups include students in engineering mathematics programs at higher educational institutions, academic staff teaching engineering mathematics in tertiary programs and research academics in the areas of technology-enhanced learning and on-line learning.

After the analysis of structure and teaching specifications of subjects related to mathematics, also characteristics and particularities of each partner's "system", and after discussing on which can be the most appropriate materials in each institution, the Portuguese team started developing of theoretical materials. It is anticipated that the interactive multimedia learning in mathematics can be a real support tool for promoting students' interest and involvement in learning through a variety of learning activities. The development process began with PowerPoint slides, which included an introduction, a background description, navigation and menu selection, and formative questions. Then the Portuguese team used the iSpring Suite 9 Software to introduce interactions, dynamic examples and exercises in the materials. In addition to correct answers to all the questions, a step-by-step solution was offered. The proposed solution is shown to students even in case they have found the right answer. With iSpring, the Portuguese team turned PowerPoint lessons into e-courses, producing 22 SCORM packages and uploading them for testing into Moodle platform. A comprehensive overview of the principles and workflow of creating learning materials was published in March 2020 [5].

The theoretical materials were supplemented by practical tests on the Moodle platform by the efforts of Estonian partners. A corresponding practice test has been created for each theory lesson, i.e. 22 practical tests have been created. Each test consists of 8-12 questions, depending on the theme. For variability each of these questions has in average 10 versions. Some versions of the question are created using the STACK question type, which generates the question with updated source data when the test is run. The question bank consists of 199 questions. So, in total considering the number of question's versions there are at least 2000 items in question bank. There are 49 close-ended type questions and 150 open-ended type questions. Exhaustive feedback has been provided for each question.

Assessment materials are a consequence of previous activities which are very interrelated. Spanish team has created around 100 questions using the iSpring software. Due to some technical limitations as students could not see their grades on the assessment table on Moodle course, fill in gaps question type did not work

properly and partially true answers were considered incorrect, the Spanish team transferred assessment tests to Moodle platform instead of iSpring.

The content of on-line course was being initially developed in English, and then translated into the languages deemed appropriate to each partner in the project. Project was being implemented in several countries of Europe: Estonia, Ireland, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain. One of the wealth of Europe is its cultural diversity, languages included. Although we are using English as a core language, and if we want complete success in each country of the project, translation to local languages is definitely necessary. The translation of the main operational content of the output to the partners' languages is facilitating optimum implementation in all the involved countries.

In order to check the validity of the decisions made, it was decided to conduct a pilot course. The pilot courses in partner countries were performed between September 2019 and February 2020. In order to assess the quality of the course materials a study was done among students that took part in the pilot course.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Questionnaire design and delivery

A survey method was selected for conducting the study. Beside the socio-demographics, questions were created to assess the student's interaction with the theory, practice and assessment materials. Most items used in the questionnaire used either 6-point or 7-point Likert scales. Students were asked to report their level of agreement with certain aspects of the course. Open ended questions were also asked to get customized feedback from students. Their open ended answers were analyzed by creating word clouds that evaluated the frequency of terms used by students. Common words that don't add value, called stop words (e.g. the, a, at, of, he, she) were removed prior to the analysis.

The questionnaire was created in English and then translated to the native languages and distributed to all partner universities. At the end of the pilot course students got the link to the online questionnaire and had to fill it in. Results were gathered by using a Google Form.

2.2 Sample description

At the time of analysis only results from Estonia, Poland, Spain, Portugal and Romania were available. A total of 95 students answered the survey.

Most students were from technical degrees (86 respondents) but also students from accounting and administration (9 respondents). Most students are young, with ages between 18 and 29 (86 respondents) but older students were also involved (ages 30 to 49 – 9 respondents). Romania had the widest spread from an age perspective. Most students had no prior experience in the course subject (44.2%), but students in some countries (Estonia, Poland and Romania) had more experience. All 8 Polish students had above average experience (scores of 4 and 5 on the 0 to 5 scale). Of the 20 Romanian students that answered the questionnaire, 12 had average experience (3 on a scale of 0 to 5) and 5 had above average experience and 5 out of

24 Estonian students had above average experience (scores of 4 and 5 on the 0 to 5 scale).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Analysis of responses

Students were asked if the theory is related to the material presented in class and if practice exercises and assessments are related to the theory. Most students found that the material is strongly related to class material. This was also true for the assessments and practice exercises. 80% and 82% of students respectively had high or very high level of agreement (ratings of 4 and 5).

Most students didn't have any difficulties at all with the material. 83% of respondents said that they had either no difficulties or very little (4 and 5 on the scale). Ten students did encounter difficulties, but each was specific without an identifiable pattern.

Students considered that they had either just the right amount of time or too much time for solving both practice exercises and during the assessment. 60% of respondents said they had just the right amount of time or slightly more (scores 3 and 4 on the scale) while 37% considered they had too much time.

Most respondents (85.6%) considered that this material will help them with the final exam (scores 4 or 5 on the scale). The distribution of answers was similar for theory, practice and assessment indicating that students consider them equally important towards their final evaluation.

Most respondents (81.4%) considered the material was moderately helpful for real life situations (scores 2,3,4 on the scale). Although they found it very useful for passing their exams, the feeling towards the material's usefulness in practice was not as strong. Students considered theoretical materials less useful in practice (14 answers of not useful at all to 10 answers for very useful) while considering practice (2 to 8) and assessment materials (3 to 8) as being useful.

Most respondents (87.4%) considered they had the right amount of materials (scores 2,3,4 on the scale). In the case of practice and assessment materials there were slightly more answers leaning towards too much materials (score 5 on the scale).

Most students (74%) agreed with the statement that the materials (theoretical, practice and assessment) were easy to use (values 4 and 5 on the scale), while 14% were moderately happy with the ease of use (score 3) and only 1% were completely dissatisfied with the ease of use. Values were distributed similarly for the theory, practice and assessment materials.

Most students (71%) liked the graphics in the theoretical material. The distribution of answers regarding the amount of text was quite uniform. There was little agreement if there was too much text in the material. Most found the platform to be intuitive (54%) and that it had a logical flow (78%). Most considered the platform easy to navigate (59%) and that they had enough information (86%). Scores of 4 and 5 were considered as agreement.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The study was conducted on a very diverse sample: students from six European countries with different ages and levels of experience. Still, the results of the pilot course suggest that the materials and tests of the engineering online course are of high quality and helpful and that students had a pleasant experience interacting with them. The theoretical materials had an appropriate amount of text and the students liked the graphics. There was more than enough time to solve assessment tests. The materials were perceived as being helpful for both their final exams and in real life even though the effect was more moderate in the later. Nevertheless, some lessons have been learned on how to better improve these materials for future courses. The students felt that more exercises and problems would improve the materials and they preferred to link the content being learned to real life situations. Results of described pilot study will be taken into account before conducting a final course. The same study will be conducted next year after the final course to get feedback on the changes made and confirmation of the results of the pilot course.

Students nowadays are leaning more and more towards practical applications in all fields, even in mathematics. Given the vast amount of information accessible to them, they need guidance in solving particular practical problems fast. The online medium is beneficial for the dissemination of information but user experience is very important to them.

A standard common course of engineering mathematics materials, assessment techniques, presentation and access are expected to impact the higher education community through facilitation and greater transferability of knowledge across the partner institutions. This approach will enable greater cooperation and understanding with similar institutions in European Union. The course structure and all supporting materials are being developed in different electronic platforms of each university for better access to the materials for students. This action ensures continued access after the project.

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